

Calculating Land Equivalent Ratio

Problem

Metrics are needed to allow the productivity of a legume-based mix of crops to be compared with crop monocultures. The land equivalent ratio expresses the performance of mixtures relative to monocultures in terms of the efficiency of land use.

Solution

The Land Equivalent Ratio (LER) is defined as the relative land area of crop monocultures required to produce the same yield as land under mixtures. It can be applied to any unit of yield (biomass, grain, nutrient) as long as the crops in a mixture are also grown in monoculture.

Benefits

Using LER to measure the relative efficiency of land use for crop mixtures allows informed decisions to be made about the costs and benefits of mixture cropping compared with monocultures.

Practical recommendation

- The crops of interest are grown on a defined plot of land as a mixture and, alongside this, plots of each crop in monoculture (Figure 1).
- The harvested product (biomass or grain) is measured for each crop in the mixture and for each monoculture, expressed as yield per unit area.
- First, the LER is calculated for each crop (sometimes termed the partial LER), by dividing the yield of the crop in the mixture by the yield of the crop in monoculture (Figure 2). The total LER is the sum of the LER values of each crop.
- LER values greater than 1 indicate more efficient land use, showing that a larger area of land would be needed in monoculture to produce the same yield as a mixture.
- LER values of 1 or less indicate no yield advantage of growing a mixture.

Applicability box

Theme

Comparing mixture with monoculture cropping

Keywords

Crop mixtures, yield, land use efficiency

Context

Annual or perennial crops, global relevance

Application time

Metric applied at harvest

Required time

Minimal

Period of impact

Within a growing season

Equipment

None

Best in

Legume-based mixtures (companion crops, intercrops)

Figure 1. Field plots of faba bean monoculture (left), wheat monoculture (middle) and faba bean-wheat mixture. (Photo: Alison Karley)

Calculation of LER for a faba bean-wheat intercrop.

LER for faba bean (LER_{bean}) = faba bean yield as a mixed crop / faba bean yield as a monocrop

LER for wheat (LER_{wheat}) = wheat yield as a mixed crop / wheat yield as a monocrop

Total LER = $LER_{\text{bean}} + LER_{\text{wheat}}$

The example below shows that 19% more land would be needed for monoculture to grow the same yield of crops achieved in a mixture.

Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Mixture	Monoculture	LER
Faba bean	3.95	5.05	0.78
Wheat	2.24	5.43	0.41
Total LER			1.19

Further information**Further reading**

The example was derived from the following publication: Tavoletti S and Merletti A (2022) A Comprehensive Approach to Evaluate Durum Wheat–Faba Bean Mixed Crop Performance. *Front. Plant Sci.* 13:733116. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2022.733116.

Weblinks

Check online resources for other examples:

<https://humblebeeorganic.com/regenerative-agriculture/the-land-equivalent-ratio-ler/>

About this practice abstract

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Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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